

Draft Genome Sequence of *Legionella pneumophila* subsp. *pneumophila* Strain DSM 25199

 Colin Hill^a

^aAPC Microbiome Ireland and School of Microbiology, University College Cork, Cork, Ireland

Neda Nezam-Abadi and Christopher J. R. Turkington contributed equally to this article. Author order was determined alphabetically.

ABSTRACT Here, we report the 3,426,844-bp draft genome sequence of *Legionella pneumophila* subsp. *pneumophila* strain DSM 25199, a serogroup 1 strain of *L. pneumophila*. The assembly consists of 24 contigs with an N_{50} of 300,843 bp.

Legionella pneumophila is the main causative agent of Legionnaires' disease, a severe pneumonia-like condition, and is capable of producing a flulike condition termed Pontiac fever (1). Serogroup 1 isolates are responsible for ~83% of culture-confirmed cases of *L. pneumophila* in the European Union and European Economic Area (2). Despite their association with this important disease, few *L. pneumophila* isolates exist within public culture collections for researchers to study (~35 *L. pneumophila* isolates are in the American Type Culture Collection [ATCC], German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures [DMSZ], and National Collection of Type Cultures [NCTC] at the time of writing), and many of these have no associated genomic data. As it is important that those isolates that are available in public collections also have readily accessible genomic information, we present the draft genome sequence of *L. pneumophila* subsp. *pneumophila* strain DSM 25199 (also known as Benidorm 030 E), a serogroup 1 strain of *L. pneumophila* available in public culture collections (ATCC 43108, DSM 25199, and NCTC 12006). Although there are no data available on the origin of this specific isolate (3), others belonging to the Benidorm 030 E subtype have been identified in instances of Legionnaires' disease (4, 5) and within environmental samples (6).

L. pneumophila DSM 25199 was purchased from DSMZ. For genomic DNA isolation, *L. pneumophila* DSM 25199 was cultured on Buffered charcoal yeast extract α -ketoglutarate (BCYE- α) agar and incubated at 37°C for 48 h. During incubation, the plate was inside a closed plastic container with a damp paper towel to produce humid conditions. Cells from an overnight incubation at 37°C in Buffered yeast extract α -ketoglutarate (BYE- α) broth were then used for DNA extraction via the GenElute bacterial genomic DNA (gDNA) kit (catalog no. NA2110-1KT; Merck) as per the manufacturer's instructions. The bacterial gDNA concentration was measured using an Invitrogen Qubit 3.0 fluorometer and the Qubit double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) BR kit. Following extraction, gDNA was sent to Novogene (Cambridge, UK) for sequencing, where DNA was fragmented and then library prepped using the NEBNext Ultra DNA library prep kit and subjected to 2 × 150-bp paired-end Illumina sequencing.

A total of 6,857,180 reads were obtained from the genome sequencing. Reads were trimmed and filtered for quality using fastp v0.23.2 (7) with the following parameters: --length_required 60 --detect_adapter_for_pe --cut_front --cut_tail --cut_window_size 4 --cut_mean_quality 20 --trim_front1 10. Sequences corresponding to the Illumina phiX spike were then removed using BBDuk from the BBMap suite (v39.01; <https://sourceforge.net/projects/bbmap/>; with parameters k=31 hdist=1). Read quality throughout this process was assessed using FastQC v0.11.9 (8) and MultiQC v1.13 (9). The 6,838,360 paired-end reads remaining after trimming and filtering were then used as input for *de novo* genome

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Address correspondence to Christopher J. R. Turkington, cturkington@ucc.ie or chrisjrt1@gmail.com.

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assembly using SPAdes v3.15.5 (10) in “--isolate” mode with default parameters. Following assembly, short contigs (<500 bp) were removed, leaving a final draft genome assembly of 24 contigs totaling 3,426,844 bp (N_{50} , 300,843 bp) with a G+C content of 38.3% and estimated average depth of $\sim 237\times$. Assembly quality was assessed using CheckM v1.2.2 (11) and found to have a completeness of 100% and contamination of 0.19%. Genome annotation was achieved using Bakta v1.6.1 (12), which predicted a total of 3,044 coding sequences, 42 tRNAs, 27 noncoding RNAs (ncRNAs), 13 pseudogenes, and 3 rRNAs. Taxonomic classification as *L. pneumophila* was confirmed using GTDB-Tk v2.1.1 (13). Prophage prediction using PhiSpy v4.2.21 (14) and hafeZ v1.0.3 (15) and plasmid identification using RFPPlasmid v0.0.18 (16) did not identify any such elements in the assembly.

Data availability. The annotated draft genome assembly of *L. pneumophila* DSM 25199 is available in GenBank under accession no. [JAQIUR0000000000](https://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/GenBank/entry/1000000000) as part of BioProject accession no. [PRJNA923147](https://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/BioProject/entry/PRJNA923147). The raw reads are deposited in the Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under accession no. [SRR23071207](https://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/SRA/entry/SRR23071207). The code and instructions to reproduce this analysis are available online at GitHub (https://github.com/Chrisjrt/Nezam-Abadi_DSM21599_genome_MRA_2023).

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